

Ten Principles to Improve Dataset Discoverability

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Abstract: The FAIR (meta) data principles provide overarching guidelines to make metadata and data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. While significant effort has been dedicated to specific recommendations that enable best practices in implementing FAIR principles, particularly from a data curation perspective, this document focuses primarily on enhancing the discoverability of data from the perspectives of data searchers and data users, including both human users and machine-based systems.

The document outlines ten principles, along with practical implementation recommendations for each principle, for improving dataset discoverability. The ten principles and recommendations are not confined to a singular community. Instead, they are applicable across a spectrum of communities since providing a data discovery service and good data discovery experience involves a shared responsibility among various stakeholders.

Impact:

The ten principles and their corresponding recommendations serve as a guide for enabling best practices in the development and enhancement of data discovery services. By providing detailed implementation guidelines, these recommendations ensure that metadata is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and that data are effectively discoverable.

Central to the principles and recommendations is the focus on users, aiming to improve a data discovery ecosystem that prioritises the user data discovery experience. The recommended implementations are designed to enhance the user's ability to find and utilise research data, thereby maximising the value of efforts in data collecting, curating, and disseminating. Moreover, these principles are also applicable to machine "users", further improving data discoverability for human users.

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Abstract

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Introduction

With the advance of open research and open data, there are more and more datasets that are published by researchers and government agencies in data repositories. These data repositories can be generalist repositories, disciplinary repositories, or institutional repositories. The FAIR (meta) data principles (Wilkinson, et al, 2016) provide high level guidelines to make metadata and data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable; there are also frameworks and practical recommendations to enable best practices in making metadata and data FAIR, yet studies show researchers have difficulty in finding datasets (Ying-Hsang et al., 2022). This paper aims to provide recommendations for data repositories to improve data discovery services from the point of views of data searchers and data users. It should be noted that these recommendations focus primarily on the discoverability aspects of data - and therefore, the access protocol to the data (so called administrative metadata, especially when dealing with sensitive data), is beyond the scope of these recommendations, as it doesn't have an impact on the discoverability process.

When searching for datasets, data seekers encounter various constraints, including their data discovery context - their specific data requirements and the context in which the data will be used. Other factors include the availability of data discovery services that may contain the desired data, the usability of such services in terms of functionality and content quality, and the recognition that data searching is not an isolated activity but rather an integral part of the research process within a broader research ecosystem.

Figure 1: General model of data discovery

[Figure 1](#) shows the key components in a data discovery service environment and how they are related to each other. Below we will discuss each component, their role in data discovery, and actors who take major responsibility for a component.

- **Data discovery context:** Data seekers (also referenced as users in this paper) are individual human beings who want to discover datasets to satisfy a data need, e.g. for a research project or to inform policy. Data seekers may search for datasets

through either a repository's discovery portal or APIs. When data seekers search for datasets, they are bounded by their search context, including their data needs - what datasets they are searching for and how they are going to use datasets, their level of knowledge or familiarity with searched datasets, and their experience with a data discovery system. This context influences how a data seeker queries, searches, and navigates through a data discovery system.

Responsibility: It is a shared responsibility of all stakeholders involved in setting up a data discovery service to elicit and understand data seekers' data discovery contexts. The stakeholders include but not limited to: 1) data providers who curate and provide access to datasets for ensuring metadata is accurate and comprehensive (more in the metadata record below), 2) providers of data discovery services, for example, repositories, catalogues, data search engines; especially user experience designers who conduct user research to understand the needs and preferences of data seekers and incorporate the findings from user research in designing intuitive and user-friendly data search and browse interfaces, 3) organisations, e.g. research institutes or funding agencies who support research endeavors, should provide resources and guidance to facilitate effective data search processes.

- **Metadata record:** A metadata record provides a description of a digital object to be searched on. A metadata record enables users to discover relevant datasets through search queries, and helps data seekers to understand the content and purpose of the described digital object.

Responsibility: Data providers and data curators take responsibility (largely if not solely) for the governance and quality of metadata records. Data provider - an individual or entity, provides metadata records to a data catalogue. Data providers may upload content to a repository/catalogue manually (e.g. Zenodo, Figshare or repositories as required by publishers or their own organisations) or set up a machine-to-machine ingest e.g. pull & push method via OAI-PMH or pull web crawl via embedded structured metadata (e.g. Schema.org) in metadata web pages. An entity who runs a data catalogue service may designate a data curator who liaison with data providers to ensure quality of metadata records.

- **Data catalogue (Data repository):** Data catalogue is a system that collects and organises metadata records in a way to make discovery service efficient and effective, as well as makes catalogued metadata interoperable with other catalogues. In this paper, we use the terms data catalogue and data repository interchangeably, where data repository provides a catalogue service, not just a data storage service.

Responsibility: It is a shared responsibility among several roles to set up and maintain a data catalogue, including: 1) data managers who develop policies and procedures for data catalog management, identify datasets to be included in the catalog, and establish data governance practices to govern access, security, and compliance; 2) IT team who provides technical expertise and support for setting up a data catalogue; 3) data providers who can provide feedback on metadata registration process; 4) data providers and subject-matter experts who make sure metadata are

properly described in the catalogue.

- Data discovery service: A data discovery service is a platform designed to enable users to find, explore, and access relevant datasets in a catalogue. Readers are suggested to refer to the user requirement of search functionalities and recommendations for data repositories in implementing the functionalities - an output of the RDA Data Discovery Paradigms IG (Wu, et al., 2019), this paper will focus on the user's requirement for metadata and presentation of a data discovery service in a broad research ecosystem.

Responsibility: Include those mentioned in setting up a data catalogue, as well as user experience designers who play a crucial role in designing the user interface and experience of the data discovery service, data users who can provide feedback on usability and effectiveness of a data discovery service.

- Data discovery in research ecosystem: A data discovery service or a catalogue doesn't exist by itself, there are many other systems and communities that can help to make each other's data more discoverable beyond a data repository. Baidi (et al., 2022) provides an overview of open ecosystems for data discovery, including scholarly communications, open data and eResearch infrastructures, research and research supporting communities.

Responsibility: Research communities and all stakeholders in supporting research and research infrastructures.

Each of the above key components plays an important role in order to provide a satisfactory data discovery experience to users, and it is shared responsibility among several roles in providing each component and making sure all components can work together as a fundamental research data support infrastructure. Making (meta) data FAIR is a primary step to identify and retrieve a dataset, however, more factors should be considered to make data discoverable from a data catalogue or over the Web, for example, to understand why - the context of a data searcher/user searches for and reuses a dataset, How should a dataset be described to match what would a data user search for, how should a data discovery system be designed in a way to facilitate and make a data search smoothly.

Through brainstorming in monthly meetings and plenary sessions of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Data Discovery Paradigms Interest Group, we come up with ten principles that provide recommended practices and examples for each of the above four components. [Table 1](#) shows a mapping of applying principles and recommendations to each component. The Table can guide readers to identify principles that are applicable to their corresponding roles.

Table 1: A mapping between the principles and each key component of the data discovery services.

Principles	User search context	Content/ Metadata	Repository discovery System	Data discovery in research ecosystem
Principle 1: Know your user	X			X
Principle 2: Improve presence in Web Search	X		X	X
Principle 3: Be present in literature search - and in user/research communities		X	X	X
Principle 4: Support both disciplinary and interdisciplinary data search		X	X	X
Principle 5: Support data searches from broad terms to narrow terms		x	X	
Principle 6: Managing Duplication of Metadata Records		X	X	
Principle 7: Search data within data		X	X	
Principle 8: Consider your users' Metadata needs		X		
Principle 9: Improve metadata quality		X		
Principle 10: Enable linked data		X	X	X

Principles for improving dataset discoverability

Principle 1: Know your user

Motivation

Providing a well-designed data discovery experience is essential for data repositories to both retain their existing users and to attract new users. This can in turn be beneficial for repositories who need to demonstrate the use of their services in order to prove a return on the investments required to maintain and develop repository services, and to motivate data providers to make their data openly findable through repository services.

Well-designed data discovery services begin with considering: 1) Who are the users a repository tries to serve? For example, Are they familiar with the repository's discovery system? Do they usually have knowledge of disciplinary areas the repository aims to serve? 2) Why do users search for data? For example, What are their data needs, what prompts them to search data from a repository in the first place, and what do they intend to do with

the data which they find? What are their data needs and how would they reuse found data? 3) How do they discover data? For example, Do they search using the interactive search features of a portal or through an API? By exploring these questions, repositories can develop data discovery services to meet actual rather than assumed needs, which can in turn lead to other benefits, e.g. increasing overall repository usage.

Recommendation

There are many established methods in areas such as user experience design, interactive information retrieval, and human-computer interaction; which data repositories can mobilise to understand the needs and search behaviours of their users. Such methods have a long history of being used to improve information discovery in library catalogues, digital libraries and web search.

The most suitable method depends on a host of factors, including available resources and time, the purpose of a study as well as the maturity and development of a repository itself (Rohrer 2022). Gathering information about users' data needs and search requirements can be achieved using questionnaires, surveys and observation; search logs and observational studies can be used to gather information about actual queries; exploring the accuracy of search results can be done by providing a search task and measuring precision and recall.

We stage a repository discovery service development process into three broad stages: 1) System/service idealisation and design, main activities are stakeholders (including users) requirement gathering, data source identification, and system architecture design; 2) New service development and a minimal viable product (MVP) online, main activities include develop MVP with consultation with stakeholders, and make the first public version online; and 3) Service refinement and evolution, when the service would get constant feedback from users, refine existing features and add new features based on feedback and availability of new technology.

During a repository's idealisation and design stage, methods such as interviews, focus groups, surveys, and system reviews can be helpful. As a repository develops and refines its services, user testing, observational studies, A/B testing and search log analyses can be conducted, although continued 'close contact' with users through qualitative approaches or user community engagement can span development phases and provide an important feedback mechanism.

Many of these methods have already been applied by both researchers and repositories to study data discovery practices. [Figure 2](#) shows some most used methods for user study. Here, we provide a few examples of how repositories have used these methods in their development of data discovery services in order to better 'know their users.'

Figure 2: Most used user study methods at different stage of data discovery service development

Recommendation 1.1: Surveys

A survey can be used to collect user data needs, functional requirements, behaviours of data discovery activities, user background, and satisfaction with a data discovery system. Incorporating an online survey at an operational data repository can help repositories to gather information about their users. One example is this [online survey](#) from Research Data Australia, a national research data discovery service offered by Australian Research Data Commons. This survey was used to collect 176 responses over 18 months. A shorter version of this survey with only two questions (regarding a respondent's job role and what type of data they were searching for) collected over 15k responses in the same time period. Together, the two surveys provided rich information about user groups and data search intentions.

Such surveys can be designed to capture quantitative data, i.e. by asking users to rank their data search experience on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from a very bad experience (option 1) to a very satisfactory experience (option 5), as in the example ([Figure 3](#)) from the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR) in Canada.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable
I like the design and layout of the website	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The website is easy to navigate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can easily find relevant information on the website	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The help documentation is useful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Searching for datasets is easy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Filters and advanced searching allows me to narrow my search terms or yields more relevant results	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The website is accessible	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 3: An example of online survey from Federated Research Data Repository in Canada

General questionnaires can also be used to create a metric for the usability of a system, e.g, the [System Usability Score](#) (SUS). Here, responses from five positive questions and five negatively-framed questions are combined and a simple calculation performed to create a single usability metric. Survey questions can also be designed to collect qualitative data by incorporating open-ended responses, such as asking users to provide more information about why they had an unsatisfactory data discovery experience.

A practical benefit of using surveys is that they can potentially collect a large sample of data at a low cost. One limitation, however, is that the data they provide are self-reported and that surveys also do not provide an opportunity to directly ask further questions to understand responses, if needed. Incorporating other methods, e.g. by complementing surveys with interviews and focus groups, can help to address this limitation.

Recommendation 1.2: Interviews

User interviews can be used to elicit in-depth user discovery context - their motivation, needs, experience, preferences etc. Repositories can invite representatives of their (potential) user communities to individual or collective interviews to learn more about their work tasks, how they search for data, and what data attributes would matter to them when they search or assess relevance of datasets.

An interview can be structured, semi-structured to open discussion. Interviewers may design interview questions to guide an interview but not necessary to conduct the interview in question/answer style. A typical interview method is the critical incident technique (Davenport 2010, Flanagan 1954), which, with the data discovery context, asks participants to recall and describe their project/activity that involves data discovery. For example, In the

study of eliciting contexts for discovering clinical trials and related health data (Liu et al. 2023), interview participants were asked to talk about a research project that required discovering and reusing data not generated by themselves, interviewers gently guided participants describe their thoughts/beliefs, activities, experiences and outcomes along each stage of data seeking, process and reusing cycle; in this way, participants often offer richer information than expected.

An interview is usually recorded and transcribed for qualitative analysis. Interview results are not usually generalizable to broader populations, and they are intended to provide an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon within a specific context. For this reason, an interview is usually an exploration tool for identifying or learning about a problem or practice in more depth. In the context of data discovery, an interview can be used for exploring the possible causes leading to a good/not so good user experience. The results of interviews can be used to inform the development of a survey with a larger population, where more participants could provide input.

Recommendation 1.3: Interaction log analysis

Interaction or search logs are recorded interactions or activities that a user conducted on an information system. Analysis of user's interactions with an information/data discovery system has been widely studied for understanding what users search for and how they search for an information discovery system through examining what queries users sent, pages clicked and paths followed; interaction patterns along certain search tasks can then be identified from aggregated individual search logs. This understanding can inform system design, interface development and information architecture construction. Previous research attempting to understand users' search behaviour has primarily focused on searching for documents or information within a Web search setting (Bhavnani 2002, Jansen & Spink 2006, Wu et al, 2008) or Digital Libraries (Gross & Taylor 2015) and searching for products on E-commerce websites (Sondhi et al. 2018). With an explosion of datasets discoverable from data repositories and on the Web, there started to have studies recently on log analysis of data search behaviors (Kacprzak, et al., 2018, Sharifpour et al., 2023).

There are tools to facilitate such an analysis such as Google Analytics, Logstash and Sematext etc. and to answer questions that are common to service providers, for example, which metadata records are most visited and if a companion of an event is successful etc. However, the analysis of native log files can provide deeper insight into user's search tactics beyond transaction statistics, and the analysis can be tailored to specific research or operational questions that a service owner would like to explore or answer. This Analytic Report (Ibáñez et al., 2020) provides a good example of conducting quantitative analysis on dataset search through more than two years of European Data Portal search and interaction logs, the analysis studied the interaction of several portal areas, e.g. query and search, facet filters, and recommended metadata fields and functionality for improving the portal.

Log analysis has its drawbacks that we can analysis recorded activities and infer some interaction patterns, however, we may not be able to explain the causes of a certain pattern without knowing users, for example, what are real intentions behind a query, why a query results in a click on a search result, why another query wouldn't, etc. This drawback can be amended by the survey study, the interview study, use experience testing or A/B test among others.

Recommendation 1.4: A/B testing

A/B testing is a method to measure preference or live impact of design changes by comparing two alternatives A and B. The two designs in comparison can range from low-fidelity that is simple and involves only low tech (e.g. wireframes) to high-fidelity that is functional and interactive (e.g. live prototype or an online product). During the design stage of a data discovery system, one can employ low-fidelity wireframes to illustrate ideas and ask potential users to compare or choose their preferred design. Once a low-fidelity design is implemented and becomes an interactive system, which can then serve as a baseline system A, a supposedly improved version of the system A can be treated as system B. There are generally two ways to conduct an A/B testing: In one method, users are recruited and asked to complete certain tasks with either System A, System B, or both, users' performance is observed and logged for comparison. In another method, two systems A and B are rotated to be the online system for interactions by random system users, users interactions are recorded and then compared. Each method has its pros and cons. The first method has its advantage that, with users' presence, testers can get more insights about why users interact with a system in certain ways by encouraging users to think aloud and/or asking users for explanations in the end; however, this method can test with only a limited number of users as it is time consuming to recruit users and conduct a testing in a "laboratory" setting. The second method can reach a large number of users, the comparison relies on quantitative analysis due to a large volume of interaction data being collected; its downside is sometimes it is not easy to explain a certain interaction pattern without being able to ask users.

Recommendation 1.5: Observation

The observation method involves observing how users carry out a data discovery task either in a laboratory setting or in their daily work environment. The method helps to collect data about what users actually did and why they did a certain way through encouraging users to think aloud and providing explanations.

During an observation, a user can be given several simulated tasks (e.g. search a specific dataset about a research topic, find all datasets from an expedition), be asked to carry out their own dataset search tasks, or a combination of both. Users can be instructed to search from 1) a specific system in order to find usability issues or evaluate specific functions, 2) two systems to compare design or functionality of two systems (this is also called A/B test), or 3) any system(s) of their own choice in order to learn what system features could help or hinder user search experience, etc. For example, Thomas et al. (2021) observed 12 social science researchers for how they searched needed data, the observations were carried out in researchers' office environment; observers recorded all observed sessions (including audios, activities on computer screen etc). They have also conducted interviews with the researchers in order to further understand the recordings. Their analysis of the recordings reveal impediments and identify opportunities for improving data discovery infrastructures.

In summary, when developing a new repository, the repository needs to understand the problem(s) it wants to address through gaining real insight into users and their needs. The repository can adopt the methods of interview, focus group and online survey, and observation for collecting use cases and prioritising key use cases to be implemented and supported.

When a repository is at more maturity stage, the repository can apply observation, interaction log analysis, or online survey to gather information about how intended users go about search datasets from the repository, what discovery features work/don't work for users, and if the repository has the content users come to search for.

Other methods also offer promise and can be incorporated at different stages in design and refinement, but have not been adopted as much in the design of data discovery services in repositories - at least in the documented literature. Card sorting (Greenberg, et al. 2023) can be helpful to learn more about how people categorize/classify data and information in order to improve the design of a web interface, while methods such as eye tracking during simulated or real searches can help repositories to gather 'cognitive data' to explore how users navigate online interfaces (Maqbali and Scholer, et al., 2013). Other methods such as A/B testing also provide a way for users to evaluate and respond to different search environments, and can provide valuable data about possible designs.

Repositories should also think in advance of how to handle any data which they create from such studies, including the purpose to which data may be put. Importance of following ethical guidelines for research conduct and a chance to consider repositories' own data management/sharing practices.

Principle 2: Improve presence in Web search

Motivation

Before a user lands on a data discovery system, they first have to find a system and know that the system has the contents they are looking for. How easy it is to do this depends greatly on a system's web presence, how well represented the system is in web search and how well metadata provided by the system is represented.

Web search is the second most common strategy to find research data (after literature - see Principle 3) (Gregory et al 2020), as indicated in [Figure 4](#), but even someone using a different strategy will very likely use web search as part of their search to stitch different information sources together (Krämer, et al 2021), especially as citations do not always use permanent identifier (although they should - see Principle 10). Many of the larger repositories see about 70% of users coming in through web search (Wu, 2022), so the goal is to make the web search as seamless as possible.

There are web tools, such as Google Search Console, that enables monitoring web-based traffic and detects problems. The tools can help to identify some usability problems (see Principle 1), their main goal is to increase web ranking. Search Engine optimization (SEO) is a catch-all term that encompasses a variety of techniques to improve the ranking. More specifically relevant for data repositories and services are the different ways to present the metadata records not only for humans, but also for automated metadata crawlers/harvesters. As a side effect, having rich, structured metadata on a metadata record's web page is known to increase the record's ranking in web search engines as well, so it pays off to do both.

Figure 4: Simplified model of the data retrieval process, without presupposing a given dataset or repository. Percentage are taken from (Gregory et al 2020) and designate strategies that researchers looking for data use often or very often.

Recommendation

We will present recommendations below that can be taken to improve web presence, roughly ordered from the most fundamental to the most advanced and data repository specific.

Recommendation 2.1: Make sure users have a chance to find the repository on its own merit

Registering a repository with a repository registry, e.g. FAIRsharing¹ and re3data², (see Principle 4), increases the repository's discoverability. For example, registering and/or claiming a registry or resources in FAIRsharing, an RDA-adopted output, and describing their content, scope and relationships will increase the citability and discoverability (by humans and machines), and the personal and organisational attribution through DOIs, ORCIDs, and ROR global identifiers³. Learn more about the FAIRsharing database registry⁴ and about FAIRsharing for resource developers and curators⁵ in their educational pages.

Build a website around a repository explaining who takes responsibility for the repository and what kind of data the repository offers, linking to other repositories with similar or connected content and asking them to link back increases the repository's discoverability. Depending on circumstances, it might be more important that users are able to find a repository than the data in the repository, for example, when the repository is not public.

Recommendation 2.2: Make sure content is indexed

When users type in the name of a dataset into the web search engine of their choice, the web page of said dataset should appear somewhere in the result list. A more scalable

¹ <https://fairsharing.org/>

² Registry of research data repositories: <https://www.re3data.org/>

³ For an example, see the GBIF record in FAIRsharing at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.zv11j3>.

⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/educational#databases>

⁵ <https://fairsharing.org/educational#developers>

version of this test is to activate Google Search Console and check the coverage, the number of indexed pages against the number of web pages one would expect given the number of datasets in the system. This may sound trivial, but over half of the repositories we asked to check this reported back that the coverage was, in fact, not 100% and in some cases less than 1%. Large repositories with millions of entries suffer from this in particular, which means that having metadata replicated at a large aggregator will not necessarily mean that that data has a website representing it. If a repository has millions of entries, the repository may need to decide, which are the most relevant.

Recommendation 2.3: Apply low level SEO measures to improve ranking

Google Search Console displays errors, e.g. around mobile usability. Use a sitemap to have more control over a repository's coverage. One can consider switching a repository's domain to something that has a high natural ranking, such as a university. Consider asking people with access to domains with a high natural ranking to link to the repositories. Get commonly used PIDs, such as DOI. Regularly check logging or web tracking (see Principle 1), if available, to find problems as they arise.

Recommendation 2.4: Include keywords

Make sure every page is self-explanatory and covers all the terms that may be used in a web search for this object (See Principle 4 and 5). This will likely include the word "dataset", any discipline specific term that describes the data or parts of the data, any names the dataset may have, including abbreviations and acronyms, keywords from controlled vocabularies and otherwise, and citation strings of literature that is closely connected to the data.

Recommendation 2.5: Embed machine-readable metadata

Include metadata not only for humans to read, but also for machines on the landing page of the PID. The simplest way to embed structured metadata in the landing page (Wu, et al., 2021), which also boosts the web search ranking.

Recommendation 2.6: Setup APIs and Harvesting

OAI-PMH is the most relevant harvesting interface, although it is not suitable for all use cases. Many repositories use specialised APIs, for example, GeoServer for sharing geospatial data with the Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW)⁶, that offer access to complex or big data or simply to make the data more accessible to machine learning algorithms. A repository's web presence should make the existence of these access options easy to find and well documented. OAI-PMH, REST or other types of data access service API endpoints can be included in the Re3data or FAIRsharing metadata record to help third-party tool developers find and use machine-actionable content (see Principle 10).

⁶ GeoServer User Manual: <https://docs.geoserver.org/main/en/user/services/csw/index.html>

Principle 3: Appear in literature search - and in user/research communities

Motivation

[Figure 4](#) indicates researchers across disciplines discover data through the academic literature, even when disciplines have existing and well-maintained data repositories and infrastructures (Gregory et al., 2020). Researchers read about data - and data repositories - in the body of publications, e.g. in methods sections where data are further introduced and discussed⁷. Researchers also follow citations to datasets from reference lists in publications; these citations can be either to individual datasets or to data repositories themselves (Gregory et al., 2023). There is a great variety in the format of data citations - in terms of objects which are cited, but also in terms of *how* these data objects are cited or mentioned (e.g. in footnotes, reference lists, or even via a citation to another academic publication).

Citing data in reference lists in standardized ways helps to make data discoverable by citation indexes. However, citation practices are in a state of development in many disciplines, and citation practices themselves follow disciplinary norms. This makes having a single standardized method for data citations challenging to implement. Encouraging (standardized) data citation involves the work of many stakeholders, including researchers, academic publishers, and data repositories (Fenner et al., 2019; Stall et al, 2023).

Recommendations

Recommendation 3.1: Provide (downloadable) data citation

A repository can work to 'be present' in the literature by clearly specifying how it prefers that others cite data and refer to the repository. This can do this by providing examples of model citations, or by including the citation for data on a record or landing page so that data users can easily identify, copy and paste and, preferably, export the citation into the tools which they already use. Recommendations from DataCite (2024), summarised and extended into a 'roadmap' for repositories to work toward data citation (Fenner et al., 2019) provide a model for components to include in recommended data citation. Important elements include the use of a unique persistent identifier that is already in use and accepted by a particular community. [Figure 5](#) shows an example from Zenodo, which provides a data citation in major styles as required by manuscript publishers⁸. Researchers who use a dataset can easily export and insert the appropriate citation style into the reference section of their manuscripts.

⁷ Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 item checklist:
<https://systematicreviewsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13643-021-01626-4/tables/2>

⁸ Citation systels: APA, MLA, Chicago, Turabian, IEEE: <https://pitt.libguides.com/citationhelp>

Figure 5: An example from Zenodo: Providing and exporting a data citation in major styles as required by manuscript publishers

Recommendation 3.2: Link dataset metadata to publications (and related research outputs)

Repositories can also work to ensure that data are linked to other forms of research output, e.g., publications but also other outputs, e.g., software. This can be done using appropriate fields in the DataCite metadata schema, e.g. “relatedItem” with a relevant “relatedItemType” from the controlled vocabulary provided by DataCite (2024). The linkage between dataset and literature in either direction increases data discoverability but also assists the construction of linked open data or knowledge graphs such as Scholix (Burton et al, 2017) and OpenAIRE (Manghi, et al, 2019) to assist more structured data discovery queries especially from machine (see Principle 10).

There are also recent efforts in data discovery to automatically detect and extract mentions of data sets in publications (Lane et al., 2020), repositories could also build on and experiment with such methods, if resources allow.

Recommendation 3.3: Engage research communities proactively

Repositories can also work to be present and visible within communities in ways which extend beyond data citations in the academic literature. Perhaps equally important - repository staff can join relevant academic societies, participate in conferences, conduct their own research, share templates and case studies to demonstrate the use of the repository, or use the repository in training materials and presentations. Such efforts make the repository itself more visible, and by extension could contribute to the discoverability of its data.

Principle 4: Support both disciplinary and interdisciplinary data search

Motivation

Scope of a research can focus on a single disciplinary, or cover multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary as research questions become more complex (Morton et al., 2015, Palmer & Cragin, 2022). Studies indicate there are differences in information seeking behaviour between disciplines, or among sub-fields of a single disciplinary (Jamali and Nicholas, 2010) due to differences in terminologies and problem solving methods (Zheng et al, 2018). Here we refer to interdisciplinary search as a need for researchers to search datasets through metadata that are described and published by other disciplines, and assume that researchers are much better in articulating their data needs from their own or familiar disciplines than in unfamiliar disciplines.

Recommendations

We provide the following recommendations for a repository that intend to support both disciplinary and interdisciplinary search:

Recommendation 4.1: Engaging intended user communities

A repository should let its targeted and wider research communities know its existence. The repository could:

- Engage with potential user communities for example by organising workshops at research conferences where researchers go to or organise data challenge events with research communities (See Principle 3)
- Improve presence in web search (See Principle 2) as researchers more likely search data from web search engines when they are not aware the existence of relevant data catalogues, and
- Register the repository to open access resources/platforms at either national (e.g. Open Data Portal of Canada, Research Data Australia) or international level (e.g. OpenAIRE, re3data, FAIRsharing).

Recommendation 4.2: Increase coverage of disciplines

If a repository aims to support multidisciplinary search, it should strive to cover as broad a range of disciplines as possible by working with data providers to increase coverage of datasets from under-presented disciplines, and by exchanging metadata from both disciplinary or interdisciplinary repositories.

Recommendation 4.3: Improve metadata interoperability and reusability

If a repository adopts a metadata schema/profile and associated vocabularies that are interoperability with other metadata schemas or standards, and encodes metadata records in a way that is machine actionable, then it will make it easy for metadata records of the repository to be harvested and indexed by other repositories, aggregators and web search engines; and this would increase the discoverability of datasets represented by the metadata records. [The WorldFAIR project](#), carried out by CODATA and RDA with nineteen partners, has been investigating the cross-domain interoperability framework (CDIF) by analysing use cases from eleven disciplines. The project published CDIF V1.0, which supplements existing standards for communicating across domain and infrastructure boundaries, for example,

CDIF recommends Schema.org and DCAT for data discoverability, and DDI-CDI⁹ for data structure, SKOS/XKOS and OWL¹⁰ for semantics and PROV-O¹¹, I-ADOPT¹² etc for data origination/context (Gregory, et al., 2024).

Recommendation 4.4: Support diverse data search terms

Support data search and filter by incorporating specific disciplinary terms to general terms (see Principle 5), and facilitate interdisciplinary research from researchers when they know what they are looking for and when they are seeing novel connections (Szostak et al. 2016, p220). Studies show that we need better metadata about disciplinary domains, as disciplinary information is important to support data discovery and citation (Gregory and Nihkov, 2022). If a repository indexes variables or vocabularies specific to a disciplinary, it is recommended to map the disciplinary vocabularies to other relevant general vocabularies, and incorporate the mapped vocabularies in index to facilitate search, search filters and browse, as the mapped vocabularies can provide a view of a different lens for viewing disciplinary framework and domain-specific language (Smith, 2020, p432).

There are also cases that a terminology has different meanings across different research disciplines. For example, in information technology, the term “network” often refers to a system of interconnected computers and devices; while in sociology, “network” can refer to social networks connecting individuals, groups. It is recommended to 1) use standard or community adopted vocabulary (ref. Recommendation 6 below) and to reference a term’s endpoint (ref. Principle 10) that provides a definition and context of a term to enable semantic search, 2) expand or refine a query that may have multiple meanings. For example, if a user searches for a dataset on “network”, the discovery system may provide options or filters for narrowing the search to “computer network” or “social network”.

Recommendation 4.5: Provide multiple data search entries

Provide a range of data discovery entry points to support users with various disciplinary knowledge and search behaviours: from simple text query to structured advanced query, advanced filters from very broad research classification to narrow research fields, from presenting a list of search result in response to a query to allow exploring dataset attributes or distributions through visualisation, etc. (Wu and Psomopoulos, et al. 2019, Dixit and Roughith, et al., 2017).

Recommendation 4.6: Provide/support machine readable metadata

A repository should aim to enhance accessibility by offering machine-readable metadata. This facilitates the seamless exchange of metadata with other repositories. Achieving this goal involves adhering to established standards for describing and encoding data properties, as well as referencing vocabularies and terms (such as measurements and variables) from a designated vocabulary service. In the event that a new vocabulary is developed and embraced by a community, it is advisable to publish and share the vocabulary through a

⁹ DDI CDI: Cross-Domain Integration: <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>

¹⁰ Using OWL and SKOS: <https://www.w3.org/2006/07/SWD/SKOS/skos-and-owl/master.html>

¹¹ PROV-O: THE PROV Ontology: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹² I-ADOPT Framework Ontology: <https://i-adopt.github.io/>

vocabulary service (e.g., ARDC Vocabulary Service¹³, CESSDA Vocabulary Service¹⁴). This practice enables others to reference the vocabulary, fostering machine-level interoperability and accessibility across multiple repositories.

Principle 5: Support data searches from broad terms to narrow terms

Motivation

A data repository get its content from various data providers who may use language specific to a discipline to describe their datasets, while users searching datasets with different contexts, for example:

- Their Information needs in dataset search are complex and can vary between very broad information needs such as “what are associated taxa?” to very specific questions such as “what butterflies occur on calcareous grassland?” (Loeffler et al, 2021).
- They have varying degrees of knowledge in a discipline. Users who are familiar with a discipline may be able to use disciplinary specific terms to describe their data needs, those who are not familiar with a discipline may tend to start with an exploratory search to investigate, evaluate or compare resources before a targeted search. An exploratory search usually uses general terms and would like to navigate a search result or a knowledge structure to identify the right terms to get what they want to search for (Lafia et al., 2023, Sharifpour, et al, 2023).

Recommendations

A repository can utilise multiple knowledge organisation structures and latest technologies to enrich its content descriptions and to support dataset search with users of different background and search context. Recommendations include:

Recommendation 5.1: Enrich content to annotate broad and narrow terms

- Subject headings - a form of knowledge classification structure is widely used by metadata schema to describe an information object, subject headings or terms are arranged hierarchically to represent broad to narrow concepts of a research or all research areas. Almost all metadata schemas or profiles adopted by data repositories have the subject field. However, not all data repositories have this subject property as a “must to have” (required field), this may result in a large proportion of data records in a repository not have a value in the subject field, and those records without a subject heading value can’t be included in advanced search, facet search and filter features that depend on a record’s subject value (Wu et al., 2021).

¹³ ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia: <https://ardc.edu.au/services/research-vocabularies-australia/>

¹⁴ CESSDA Vocabulary Service: <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/>

A repository can enforce the subject field as must to have or use latest AI/ML technologies to annotate its metadata records with vocabularies from its adopted subject classification schema (Zhang et al., 2023). Repositories can scan existing vocabulary services for a standard or community adopted subject classification schema, for example, [NERC Vocabulary Service](#), [ARDC Research Vocabulary Australia Basic Registry of Thesauri, Ontologies and Classifications](#), [Bioportal \(Life Sciences\)](#), [Agroportal \(Agricultural Science\)](#), [BiodivPortal \(Biodiversity\)](#)(Biodiversity), [Unified Medical Language System \(UMLS\)](#), to name a few for example.

- Many standard subject classification schemas are in multi-lingua, indexing equivalent subject headings in multiple languages enables users to query in their own language. For example, knowledge graphs such as Wikidata provide different languages in English, Chinese and Italian (an example for Apis (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q102857>); and EuroVoc provides over 20+ languages for its vocabulary terms (see an example for the term Energy: <https://op.europa.eu/s/y2aR>).
- Some terminologies also support common names and alternate labels (e.g., different spellings). This is in particular helpful for novice users or users with a different research background. Metadata descriptions are usually provided by domain experts and often contain scientific terms or formulas. Adding common terms and alternate labels to metadata descriptions enhance dataset discovery for non-experts (Loeffler et al, 2017).
- A repository is recommended to support multiple subject classification schemas to best serve its targeted data searcher communities and general audiences, as shown in [Figure 6](#); as a single subject headings may not satisfy diverse dataset search needs. For example, a repository adopting subject headings for classifying all research areas (e.g. ANZSRC-FoR) may not be able to support researchers who search for clinical trials that are about specific medication conditions and may want to consider concurrently implementing MeSH or other subject authorities (e.g. ANZCTR Conditions in [Figure 6](#)) to support more sophisticated searches of broader/narrower medical terminology.

Recommendation 5.2: Enhance data search functionality

- Provide a range of query interfaces (from simple search box to advanced search) and multiple discovery mechanisms (search, subject browse, faceted browse/filtering) (Wu et al., 2019).
- Expand a query to include broad or narrow terms. For example, if a search result on a concrete species results in no matched metadata record, the query can be expanded to a broad term about the searched species. Studies indicate that users appreciate this support (Löffler, et al., 2023). The expanded query terms can be from the repository adopted subject classification schemas, terms from its user community, for example, repository's search logs of past query and reformulated query associations (reference), a community's question and answering posts (Terolli et al., 2020).

Figure 6: An example of filters combining general Subjects headings and disciplinary specific classification schemas (ANZCTR Conditions)

If an automatic search term expansion is performed, ensure that it is *transparent* to the user by showing exactly what query terms are added. This transparent communication helps the user to understand the search result, but also to help the user record the expanded query and reproduce the search if required. A good example would be how one is able to access the raw expanded search syntax generated from a broad search in Pubmed ([Pubmed documentation on Saving Your Search](#)). As such information about query is required to be included in papers such as [cochrane reviews](#). However, it is not necessary to display all technical details (e.g., SPARQL queries). A recent study has shown that users prefer simple explanations on the expanded terms (Löffler, et al., 2023).

- Instead of expanding the query, full-text search engines perform better when the content is enriched during indexing (or a combination of both). When enriching the content (e.g. from either user or machine, ref. Principle 8), make sure to use separate auxiliary search engine fields for the enriched terms to allow correct result ranking by applying query boosts on the original and auxiliary field queries, so exact hits on the original field can be ranked higher.

Principle 6: Manage Duplication of Metadata Records

Motivation

A repository may have duplicated metadata records, as well as duplicated datasets. Atzori (2016) provides a review of datasets deduplication tools. In this principle, we focus on metadata records of the same dataset or a data product being revisioned, as having

duplicated metadata records of the same datasets hinders on user data search experience (Liu, et al., 2023). For example, Having too many duplicates in a search result can consume users' time as they navigate through the research result, follow data access links, or even spend effort downloading datasets only to encounter the same dataset. Addressing the application issue takes the responsibility of all parties - data repository providers, data author/provider, publisher, and PID provider. For example, DOI mint service providers could prevent the allocation of duplicated DOIs for the same or nearly the same metadata records when receiving a new DOI request, or flag possibly duplicates for further inspection.

Recommendations

Recommendation 6.1: Know the cause of duplicated records

Duplicate metadata records of the same data object may exist in different forms, as following:

- Duplicated records - these metadata records have exact the same content. This may result in a repository aggregating metadata from different sources that cross-harvest metadata records from each other.
- Parallel records - two metadata records describe the same data object but the two records don't overlap with each other completely. This may result from a dataset being described in different languages, or co-authors of a dataset working for different institutions and thus submitting and describing the dataset in their own institutional repositories, these records are then harvested by the same downstream data catalogue/aggregator.
- Augment records - a metadata record is an augment of another, one record has the other records's content as a subset. This may result from a record of one repository being augmented and enriched by another repository that may change dataset format, or two repositories use different metadata schemas; or a data product has been under revision - with minor revision that may not change the data product itself but the product metadata recorded the changes (USGS, 2023).

Understanding the types, causes, and occurrences of duplications in a repository is crucial for developing an effective data curation policy. This knowledge informs the repository to implement tailored methods specifically designed to address the relevant types of duplicates.

Recommendation 6.2: Strive to use the same DOI or to link to the primary DOI

Having a persistent identifier for the same data object or linking metadata records (regardless of the above type) of the same objects makes it easier to identify these records. This requires repositories to follow a similar procedure or provide the similar guidelines to their data depositors when a dataset is published to a repository. For example, when authors/researchers register a dataset to a repository, they could be asked if the same dataset has been published at other repositories. If yes, data authors can register the dataset by simply providing the DOI or the dataset citation information (which includes DOI), the repository can use the DataCite API to retrieve the metadata record of a given DOI¹⁵. If a repository doesn't offer such a DOI registration and retrieval service or requires a metadata in a language different from originally published one (parallel records), then the repository

¹⁵ DataCite REST API Guide: <https://support.datacite.org/v1.3/docs/api>

should allow the linkage of duplicated or nearly metadata records through the relation such as *IsIdenticalTo* (DataCite, 2024).

Recommendation 6.3: Versioning augmented metadata records

When a repository has augmented a metadata record from its original source, the augmented metadata record can link to its original metadata record, preferably in a structured way (e.g. through related objects if metadata schema allows), for example, *HasMetadata* from the DataCite schema (2024). Some repository may treat an augmented metadata record as a new version, in this case, an augmented version can be linked to its previous version, for example, *isVersionOf* (or *isNewVersionOf*, *IsPreviousVersionOf*), as well as with indication that new version is about metadata record not the dataset (Klump et al., 2021)

Recommendation 6.4: Utilise technology to identify and manage duplicates without the same or linked PID

A repository can use PID to identify duplicates. However, despite all efforts, a procedure and guidelines may not be followed, a repository may end up with the duplicated/parallel/augmented records of the same dataset with different PIDs/DOIs. And it is understandable, a repository couldn't remove or link duplicates due to data publishing agreement with upstream data providers/repositories. In this case, the repository can resort to other means, for example, using natural language processing tools to compare the similarity of the two records, feedback for users to tag duplicated records they identify.

Identified the three types of records could be agglomerated as one group in a search result (or as one super node in a research object graph) or when in displaying the dataset information. [Figure 7](#) shows an example from Google dataset search, the search results of the query "water salinity" (left panel) indicates how many records/sources exist for a dataset, and the dataset information display (right panel) clear indicates the six sources/repositories that provide the information, a user can select one familiar source to go to, either access more information or download the dataset. (it seems that none of the six sources provide DOI to the dataset, one source server is down). For repository search engines based on Apache Lucene (e.g., Apache Solr, Elasticsearch, Opensearch), features like "result grouping" / "field collapsing" / "top docs aggregation" can be used to display search results in a similar way like Google Dataset search allows. This still requires that the schema/mapping used by the search engine allows the application of these technologies. A quick way to identify possible duplicates is the "more like this" functionality provided by the full text search engine which may be used to identify possible "groups". This is a well known technique also used in shopping portals to groups similar product search results based on their metadata / description.

Figure 7: An example of aggregating duplicated metadata records from several data catalogues

Principle 7: Provide and link metadata at different granular levels

Motivation

It is important to recognize the importance of distinguishing between study-level metadata and variable-level metadata. Study-level metadata provides an overview of the entire dataset, while variable-level metadata offers specific information about individual data points. By enabling users to search within both levels, researchers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the dataset and make more informed decisions based on the quality and relevance of the metadata. However, this distinction can be further refined only in particular types of (meta) data; for example, while numeric/structured data often lends itself well to in-depth exploration, text-based data are traditionally much harder to structure and properly annotate. Finally, it is important to connect this to the concept of data granularity; by providing the means to search within data at different levels of granularity, researchers can refine their queries and focus their analysis on specific subsets of the dataset. This flexibility allows for a more nuanced exploration, enabling users to uncover patterns, relationships, and contextual information that might otherwise remain hidden.

Recommendations

Recommendation 7.1: Describe a dataset at different granular levels (e.g. collection, item, variable)

In order to address these challenges, an initial approach would be to implement comprehensive data annotation. Specifically, data repositories could prioritize the

implementation of comprehensive data annotation strategies to distinguish between study-level metadata and variable-level metadata, for example, a poll/survey data on a national election can be described in the study-level metadata, while each individual survey questions or variables are usually captured inside a data file; nevertheless each individual questions or variables (e.g. suburb or age group) have the possibility to be reused and combined with other data, they should be added to the study-level metadata for being indexed. The same applies to collection-level metadata and item-level metadata, for example, a collection about Theodore Roosevelt may contain photographs, video recordings and speeches of him, while a historian may want to find photos “Theodore Roosevelt on a horse” (Wendler, 2004). In this context, study-level metadata should provide an overview of the entire dataset, including its context, purpose, and data sources, while variable-level metadata should offer specific information about individual data points, such as data type, variables, units, and any transformations applied. This detailed annotation ensures that researchers can quickly assess the relevance and quality of the data, facilitating more informed decisions about dataset selection. For example, in a climate science dataset, study-level metadata would include information about the geographic region covered, the time period, and the research objectives; variable-level metadata, on the other hand, would detail specific variables such as temperature, humidity, or precipitation, providing units of measurement and the methods used for data collection. A more concrete example is the case of PANGAEA (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02269-x>), where collection datasets (see also RDA Complex Data Citation Working Group) get a slightly higher preference in the search result, while sub-level datasets always include a reference to the collection or parent dataset. Collection datasets summarize the metadata of sub-level datasets which are often differently structured datasets with specific measurement types, but still depend on each other (“bundled publication”, e.g., Rudaya, Natalia (2020): Pollen and diatom records of Lake Big Yarovoe in Kulunda, southern West Siberia, Russia, covering 4 ka. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.914589>). This allows users to cite the whole bundle if required, but still refer to the sub-level datasets for a more detailed discovery using an “In:” citation, also commonly used when citing book chapters ([Figure 8](#)).

By enriching collection level datasets with important terms and concepts from the sub-level datasets can help search engines to rank item-level metadata records (Foulonneau, et al., 2005) search engine users can easily find the collection which allows them to download the whole collection in one go instead of each sub-level dataset.

Recommendation 7.2: Using structure metadata to link resources at different granular levels

NISO (2004) classifies metadata elements into three types: descriptive, administrative, and structural. Descriptive metadata is used for discovery; administrative metadata is for managing, preserving, and accessing objects in a repository; and structural metadata shows types, structure, and relationships of resources or parts of a resource to one another, the relations can be about sequence, an item in hierarchy, etc. For example, a time series data with datasets covering certain time intervals and a dataset in different versions. In the web and linked data discovery context, this structure metadata can be used to assist navigation by both human and machine ([Figure 8](#)).

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Citation: **Rudaya, Natalia (2020):** Age-depth relation of sediment core 2008-3 from Lake Big Yarovoe in Kulunda, southern West Siberia, Russia. *PANGAEA*, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.914875>,
In: Rudaya, N (2020): Pollen and diatom records of Lake Big Yarovoe in Kulunda, southern West Siberia, Russia, covering 4 ka. *PANGAEA*, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.914589>

Always quote citation above when using data! You can download the citation in several formats below.

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Abstract: In 2008, a 404 cm long sediment core (2008-3) was recovered from 8 m depth in the southern part of Lake Big Yarovoe. It consists mostly of striated black, grey and greenish-grey silts. The poor organic content of Lake Big Yarovoe sediments posed a problem for radiocarbon dating, but the problem was solved with a geomagnetic approach. A record of geomagnetic inclinations from the studied core was compared with Holocene records of inclinations from Lake Biwa, Japan. The age model of Lake Biwa is based on two widespread tephra layers: Kawagodaira (3.15 ka BP) and Kikai-Akahoya (7.25 ka BP) (Ali et al., 1999). To produce an adequate age-depth model for Lake Big Yarovoe, we transferred the ages of the extremes that the two geomagnetic curves have in common from the Lake Biwa age model to the Lake Big Yarovoe record. For more detailed information see Rudaya et al., 2012.

Keyword(s): Holocene; vegetation history; Western Siberia

Figure 8: An example of a sub-level dataset which refers to a collection

A repository is recommended to adopt a metadata schema that provides vocabulary to describe needed structured metadata. The relation vocabulary can include general relations, e.g. same as, relate to, citation, part of, mention, version; or relations specific to a domain, e.g. relations between different species: mutualism, commensalism, parasitism, and competition. This structure metadata can be used to organise related resources, assist research result ranking (e.g. a dataset is linked to many related resources or publications can be boosted to rank higher), and guide user's exploratory navigation, and enables linked data (See Principle 10).

Recommendation 7.3: Provide flexible data search interfaces

Finally, it is critical to allow for flexible data search interfaces. Such search interfaces would allow researchers to explore data at different levels of granularity. The search functionality should accommodate variations in data types, recognizing that searching within text-based data differs significantly from searching within numeric or structured data. By offering versatile search options, repositories empower users to refine their queries and uncover hidden insights within datasets. For example, the OGC API – EDR Standard (<https://ogcapi.ogc.org/edr/overview.html>) makes it easy to access a wide range of data through a uniform, well-defined, simple Web interface that provides users with purely the data they require while shielding them from the complexities of the underlying data storage technologies. A major use case for an EDR API is to retrieve small subsets from large collections of environmental data, such as weather forecasts, though many other types of data can be accessed. The important aspect, in this case, is that the data can be unambiguously specified by spatio-temporal coordinates.

Principle 8: Consider your users' Metadata needs (from user's perspective)

Motivation

It is desirable yet costly to have comprehensive metadata about a dataset. Priority/consideration should be given to the use cases that matter most to a repository, for example, who are the targeted user groups (both human and machine), what metadata attributes are important to them when they search and reuse datasets, and how metadata should be encoded for machine to process.

Recommendations

Recommendation 8.1: Find user's metadata need through user study

The way to find metadata needs is through user study. Principle 1 recommends several methods that can be tailored to find out the user's metadata needs. Different methods can be chosen depending on the purpose and the stage of a repository development. For example, Dixit (et al., 2017) applied first interview with researchers for identifying user information/metadata needs before the development of DataMed - a data discovery index, and then conducted iterative usability evaluation of search functionality, vocabulary mismatch, and metadata (present or missing) that can help or hinder a user's search experience. Through this process, they collected their user's metadata needs, including biomedical concepts, data type, data format, sample description, intervention/study design, variables, et al. among others.

Recommendation 8.2: Balance between generalist repository and disciplinary repository

A balance should be considered between generalist repository and discipline/domain repository. Both types of repository could share a common set of metadata attributes, meanwhile allow the use of domain-specific attributes to satisfy a wide range of data discovery needs and users with different degrees of domain knowledge (ref. Principle 4 and 5). This RDA data discovery paradigms IG collected about 79 use cases on researchers' data discovery needs regardless of research domains (de Waard et al, 2017). The use cases were then analysed and clustered into three groups: needs for metadata, data and portal functionality (Wu, et al., 2019), the needs for metadata and data indicate desired metadata attributes, including provenance information, geographic and temporal coverage, accessibility and publication linkage, etc. Löffler (et al., 2021) examined those research questions that led to dataset search, specifically to the research field of diversity, they identified important domain-specific metadata on biodiversity domain environments, materials and chemicals, species, biological and chemical processes, locations, data parameters and data types. In a similar vein, Queralt-Rosinach (et al, 2023) collected metadata needs for the case of synthetic health data, where the variables represented in the data (e.g., tissue, age, population) could help researchers better understand the datasets at hand. Metadata on the variables has an increased value when it comes to private or sensitive data when data cannot be directly accessed. The metadata becomes a door for researchers to decide whether they should get access to the data (which in some cases could require Non-disclosure agreements, membership or payment). These metadata are well covered in domain-specific standards, yet large data repositories tend to use

domain-independent metadata fields that don't cover well the need for domain-specific dataset search.

Recommendation 8.3: Involve users in metadata enrichment and improve metadata quality

User's need for metadata can be captured from the user themselves. Traditionally, users are consumers of metadata and data, however, they can also be involved in enriching metadata and improving metadata quality. A metadata that is added and regarded as important by one user may have similar importance for other users. Repositories can provide tools for users to add their own annotation to a dataset's metadata record (Gursoy et al., 2018), for example, they could add (or correct) subject metadata, different names of a species, geo-location; or provide feedback on what is desired but missing information in a metadata record. The tool as such could be as simple as a "suggested change" link or more advanced solution as how GitHub works, where there is an issue tracker where problems could be discussed and a pull request system where specific changes could be suggested, discussed, and merged if there is consensus. This would encourage active domain-specific engagement and enable tailored fulfillment of domain-specific metadata needs.

Recommendation 8.4: Utilise latest AI technologies to enrich metadata

Similarly, latest AI technologies can also be utilised to enrich metadata, as well as to provide alternative multilingual versions (Matusiak, et al., 2015). Research shows AI and ML can be used to automate subject annotation and index (Golub 2021, Wu, et al., 2023). The availability of pre-trained large language models makes available resources and low barriers for repositories to adopt the latest AI technology for automated metadata annotation (Suominen, 2023), although human touch may need to be involved to monitor any kind of bias. AL and ML technologies have also been long applied to improve information discovery on the web, Sharifpour et al. (2023) demonstrated to apply ML technologies to analyse their users' dataset search behavior of a data catalog, and thus improve dataset discovery service and user experience.

Principle 9: Improve metadata quality

Motivation

Metadata quality, like data quality, refers to "fitness for purpose". Thus, metadata quality has several dimensions or criteria depending on the purpose of its intended use (e.g Lawrence et al. 2009, Statistics Canada 2002), and Accuracy, Completeness and Consistency are the most common and important criteria for digital collections (Park, 2009).

Factors that impact on metadata quality include: schema level, record level, syntax level; which are discussed in the recommendations below.

Recommendations

Recommendation 9.1: Select a schema and standard (or community adopted) vocabularies that enable the description of data properties users need

The creation or selection of a metadata schema. A schema enables the description of different types of metadata. Riley (2017) metadata taxonomy includes descriptive metadata, administrative metadata (including Technical, Preservation and Rights metadata), structural metadata and markup languages. Among them, the descriptive metadata (about the dataset itself) and structural metadata (contextual relationships to other digital objects) are mostly important for finding and understanding a dataset, with the descriptive metadata being indexed for search, and structural metadata for linking and browsing and enabling more dataset search query options than text queries as imputed in a search box.

Schema should include those elements/properties that users need (ref. Principle 8) and use standard controlled vocabularies whenever possible. For example, subject headings from MESH.

Recommendation 9.2: A metadata record should be accurate to reflect the dataset and strive to be as complete as the schema allows

The creation of a metadata record for a dataset: when a metadata record is created under the chosen schema, the record should be accurate to reflect the dataset and strive to be as complete as the schema allows. Low metadata quality usually refers to a metadata record that contains fewer metadata elements, for example, a metadata record doesn't include a description (or abstract) or subject headings. A catalogue should make explicit which metadata fields are must to have for meeting the data discovery need, and provide data providers a quality check tool or report, for example, [data.europa.edu developed its metadata quality assessment tool](#). (Wentzel, 2023)

Other poor quality metadata records include: poorly written description without considering data seekers' familiarity with written terminologies (ref. Principle 4 & 5), a metadata element without using standard values (e.g. subject headings, variable names from a community endorsed dictionary), or inconsistent naming of variables or concepts. Having poor or inconsistent metadata records in a repository harms retrieval of relevant records and linkage of related records, thus impacting the user's data search experience.

Recommendation 9.3: Use validation tools to detect syntax errors

Syntax are the principles for how metadata elements and their content should be structured and encoded/marked-up. For example, XML, JSON, and RDF are common syntax. A metadata schema can be expressed in different syntax. With a proper syntax enhances metadata consistency from the same repository and interoperability across repositories. A proper and validated syntax enhances metadata interoperability and reusability, increasing the possibility of enriching metadata with additional information.

Schema validation tools can detect syntax errors that could prevent the metadata records

with encoding errors being processed correctly. For example, DCAT-AP¹⁶ validation (<https://data.europa.eu/mqa/shacl-validator-ui>) or the German profile of DCAT-AP - DCAT-AP.de validation (<https://www.itb.ec.europa.eu/shacl/dcat-ap.de/upload>).

Data repositories could consider using proper tools to check completeness and consistency of metadata records, and provide guidance to metadata providers on the creation of metadata records of high quality.

Recommendation 9.4: Evaluating FAIRness of metadata quality for further improvement

The FAIR (meta)data principles provide guidelines for making metadata FAIR. The above three recommendations provide practical guidelines to improve FAIRness of metadata, there are a number of tools that can help to assess FAIRness of metadata implementation and thus identify gaps for future improvements. Here are some Framework and tools:

- FAIRassist (<https://fairassist.org/>) provides a listing of the known FAIR assessment and evaluation tools, many of which use repository-level metadata from FAIRsharing's API to determine the FAIRness of a digital object within that repository.
- Work is ongoing among a number of FAIR evaluation tools and FAIRsharing within the EOSC FAIR Metrics Task Force (Wilkinson et al., 2022) to ensure FAIR assessment is contingent upon appropriate, shared, metrics. Registering with FAIRsharing (see also Step 2) exposes repositories' metadata in a machine-actionable way that will ensure they are evaluated properly in these assessment tools.
- Tools are developed to assess metadata quality. For example, The metadata quality assessment tool (<https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology>) helps to assess metadata quality and provide an assessment report to data providers who ingest metadata to European Data portal (data.europa.eu); the quality includes the completeness of a metadata record in complies with DCAT-AP, and accessibility of dataset download URL, and machine readability of the reference data.
- A FAIRness quality maturity matrix is offered as a structured, tired, and progressive approach to evaluating and reporting the degree of metadata, data and infrastructure FAIR-compliance (Peng, et al., 2024).

Repositories should identify tools and matrices that fit their own metadata (and data) FAIRness assessment purpose, assessment could result in a roadmap for further improvement.

Recommendation 9.5: Apply machine learning for metadata extraction

We can leverage machine learning and the latest advances in large language models for metadata extraction and annotation. Machine learning models, trained on a diverse range of data types, can be used to recognise patterns and structures within the data, ensuring metadata consistency and completeness (Wu et al., 2023). For example, Natural Language Processing (NLP) models can extract variable-level metadata from unstructured text data by identifying key entities, such as dates, locations, and measurements, providing structured

¹⁶ DCAT Application profile for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP): <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

information that facilitates search and analysis. Automated annotation quality could be increased with manual curation and the incorporation of “evidence tags” in the metadata (such as curated/manual/automatic), therefore clarifying provenance and resolving any conflicts that may arise. Automated annotation has, of course, some clear risks that could increase the overall cost of maintenance.

Principle 10: Enable linked data

Motivation

Linked data is structured data which is interlinked with other data so that more data can be discovered through links (Berners-Lee, 2006). Describing a metadata element and value in a linked data manner enhances metadata interoperability and reusability for machine processing, increases the possibility of enriching metadata with additional information (e.g., linkage to profiles of a researcher, the respective publication, multimedia files and source code), and thus improving data discoverability through the exposure of rich metadata to a wider audience and applications (Bahnemann et al. 2021).

Linked data builds upon standard Web technologies such as URIs, HTTP, and RDF. The key principles that Linked Data builds on are: use URIs as names for things; use HTTP URIs so that people can look up those names; when people look up a URI, they get useful information about a thing, using the standards (RDF¹⁷, SPARQL¹⁸, SKOS¹⁹, JSON-LD²⁰); and include links to other URIs so that they can discover more things (Berners-Lee, 2006). The linked data conceptual model and technologies have been adopted by the library community for describing library resources, e.g. bibliographical data, teaching and training materials. The guides (LOC Linked Data Service²¹, Subirats and Zeng, 2020) produced by the community can be referenced by research data communities when describing dataset and associated resources in accordance with the linked data principles.

The application of JSON-LD and Schema.org can significantly extend the benefits of linked data by simplifying the integration and sharing of structured data across different repositories. JSON-LD, a lightweight Linked Data format, makes it easier for developers to serialize and link data without needing extensive knowledge in semantic web technologies. It allows data to be nested and linked in a way that is both human-readable and machine-processable. Schema.org, on the other hand, provides a shared vocabulary that can be used with JSON-LD to describe things and relationships on the Internet in a more consistent way. This harmonisation not only enhances the discoverability of repositories contents by making it more SEO friendly but also increases the potential for metadata enrichment and reusability across different domains. By leveraging JSON-LD and Schema.org, repositories can expose their data more effectively, enabling a wider range of applications to understand and process the information.

¹⁷ Resource Description Framework: <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

¹⁸ SPARQL 1.1 Query Language: <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>

¹⁹ SKOS Simple Knowledge Organisation System: <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>

²⁰ JSON for Linked Data: <https://json-ld.org/>

²¹ Library of congress, ID.LOC.GOV - Linked Data Service <https://id.loc.gov/>

Recommendations

Recommendation 10.1: Allocate/mint Persistent Identifiers in your metadata so that your data can be linked by others

Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI), or Internationalised Resource Identifiers (IRIs, a generalisation of URIs) is a fundamental concept of the linked data, it is commonly implemented in the form of URLs or IRIs, which specify the location of a resource on the Web. Persistent identifier (e.g. DOI) and handle are types of URIs and widely used to identify research inputs, processes, and outputs. PIDs are essential for enabling Linked Data and providing the underlying data to construct Knowledge Graphs. Underlying standardized vocabularies help to reference concrete objects such as people, locations, projects and data objects as well as nonspecific abstract terms, e.g., genes, organisms or chemical compounds. These referenced entries in vocabularies (non-instance level) or Knowledge Graphs (with instances) support context search, such as in the EU Knowledge Graph (Diefenbach, et al., 2021) with its application Kohesio (<https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu>). Examples for scientific knowledge graphs are for instance the PubMed Knowledge Graph (Yu et al, 2020) or Knowledge Graph for precision medicine (Chandak et al, 2023).

It is recommended for a repository to

- Allocate/mint a persistent identifier for any objects in the repository: for example, DOI for grant, project, dataset, software code and tool, publication, report, project/research activity, instrument; ORCID for researchers, ROR for institutions, IGSN for samples.
- Publish a vocabulary as open vocabulary (e.g. [Linked Open Vocabularies](#)), and domain specific vocabularies should be published in a domain-specific repository if possible, for example, Bioportal for biomedical ontologies (<https://www.bioontology.org/>). If a suitable open vocabulary (e.g. for measurements specific to a discipline) can't be found so the vocabulary can be referenced by others (see an example in the Recommendation 2 below).

Recommendation 10.2: Reference existing Persistent Identifiers or URIs of other's data

Linked open data eliminates the necessity to provide comprehensive descriptions for every aspect of a dataset. The general principle is that if an object has already been described elsewhere, there's no need to duplicate its description unless additional information can enhance the original metadata. A metadata record can include persistent identifiers of associated resources and attributes, for instance, authors and organizations receiving grants can be referenced through ORCID or ROR, respectively (see an example below), rather than duplicating information such as names, affiliations, and locations. Linking to established and authoritative records minimizes data entry costs and reduces inconsistency resulting from variations in how the same information is expressed across multiple metadata records.

For example, when providing information of a dataset creator, reference the creator's identifier:

```
"creator":{
  "@type":"Person",
  "givenName":"Peter",
  "familyName":"Smith",
  "sameAs":"http://orcid.org/0000-0000-0000-0000"
}
```

Include URIs from (controlled) vocabularies that are published as linked data (e.g. <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/> or <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>); consider publishing a vocabulary as a linked data and reference a vocabulary term with its URI.

For example, instead of encoding subject of a publication as a string:

```
"subjects": ["geology", "soil sciences"]
```

Identify suitable terms from open vocabulary and reference URI of a term:

```
"subjects":[
  {
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "url": "http://purl.org/au-research/vocabulary/anzsrc-for/2008/0403",
    "Name": "geology",
    "termCode": "0403",
    "inDefinedTermSet": "https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/repository/api/lda/anzsrc-for/concept"
  },
  {
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "url": "http://purl.org/au-research/vocabulary/anzsrc-for/2008/0503",
    "name": "Soil Sciences",
    "termCode": "0503",
    "inDefinedTermSet": "https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/repository/api/lda/anzsrc-for/concept"
  },
  {
    "@type": "DefinedTermSet",
    "url": "https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/repository/api/lda/anzsrc-for/concept",
    "name": "ANZSRC Field of Research Vocabulary Service (ABS 1297.0)"
  }
]
```

By employing standardized vocabularies to describe metadata properties and values, and by incorporating Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) within metadata records, one can establish a framework conducive to transforming and publishing these records as linked data (W3C 2014). This foundation remains effective even if the record is not originally expressed in RDF, Turtle, or JSON-LD – the typical syntaxes associated with linked data.

Conclusion

We presented ten principles and recommendations in implementing principles for enabling best practices in developing a data discovery service. Recommendations of some Principles provide detailed implementation guidelines to make metadata FAIR, for example, Principles 4, 5 and 8 provide recommendations on describing data with rich metadata (F2 - Data are described with rich metadata), metadata meet domain-relevant community standards (R1.3). Recommendations from some principles are beyond the FAIR principles (e.g. Principle 1).

All ten principles place users in the foci of a data discovery ecosystem, with the aim to improve the usability and efficiency of data discovery services, thus to maximise the value of efforts in collecting, curating, and disseminating research data. These principles are also applicable to machine “users”, facilitating data discovery for machines ultimately enhances accessibility for human users.

The introduction section provides a mapping between ten principles and key components of the data discovery service. The ten principles are not limited to a single community governed by a solitary principle, such as data curation. Rather, they are applicable across a spectrum of communities, as offering a data discovery service entails a shared responsibility among various stakeholders.

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